

Optimized surface gratings for high-speed polarization switching in spin-VCSELs

OLIVER JAN HEJTMAN,^{1,*}
AND MACIEJ DEMS³

¹*Faculty of Materials Science and Technology, VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic*

²*Nanotechnology Centre, CEET, VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, 17. Listopadu 21712/15, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic*

³*Institute of Physics, Lodz University of Technology, ul. Wólczańska 217/221, 93-005 Łódź, Poland*

**oliver.jan.hejtman@vsb.cz*

Abstract: Vertical-cavity surface-emitting lasers are limited to 30–50 GHz in conventional intensity modulation. Polarization modulation offers a promising alternative, exploiting birefringence-induced oscillations at much higher frequencies. We use rigorous coupled-wave analysis to design monolithic surface gratings that engineer birefringence for ultrafast modulation while minimizing loss anisotropy. By optimizing grating parameters and cap layer thickness, we achieve frequency splitting over 280 GHz with practical photon lifetimes and crucial near-zero dichroism. This work demonstrates a compact, fabrication-ready solution for birefringence control in spin-VCSELs, enabling their application in ultrafast polarization-based optical data transmission.

Published by Optica Publishing Group under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Further distribution of this work must maintain attribution to the author(s) and the published article's title, journal citation, and DOI.

1. Introduction

VCSELs (Vertical-Cavity Surface-Emitting Lasers) are widely used across a range of industries, from optical interconnects [1,2] and consumer electronics to 3D sensing applications [3,4], including face recognition and automotive systems. Their small footprint and low power requirement also make them valuable for photonic integrated circuits [4–6]. Key advantages, such as compactness, circular beam profile, temperature stability and easy fabrication of two-dimensional arrays make them ideal for these applications. Ongoing developments in metastructures are pushing the boundaries of VCSEL performance, particularly for next-generation data communication. In this context, the ability to control and switch polarization plays a crucial role in enabling ultrafast data transfer, addressing the growing demand for high-speed interconnects.

In conventional VCSEL-based optical communication, intensity modulation (IM) dominates data encoding, where information is transmitted through variations in optical power. However, IM bandwidth is fundamentally constrained by photon lifetime and carrier dynamics, typically reaching practical limits of 30–50 GHz in optimized VCSELs [4,7,8]. While increasing photon density via higher pumping can enhance bandwidth, it also leads to increased power dissipation and heating. An alternative approach involves using small-mode-volume nanocavity geometries, where photon density is enhanced at cryogenic temperatures without requiring high pump power [9].

To overcome these constraints, spin-VCSELs with polarization modulation (PM) have emerged as an alternative, leveraging rapid oscillations between two orthogonal polarizations controlled by spin injection. The key mechanism is ultrafast optical switching via coupling between carrier spin and photon spin [10]. A short spin relaxation time $1/\gamma_s$ is essential for high-speed switching. GaAs active material provides spin-flip rates γ_s exceeding 1000 ns^{-1} , enabling PM frequencies $\tilde{\nu}$

of up to 500 GHz [11–13]. The modulation frequency $\tilde{\nu}$ in PM is governed by frequency splitting $\delta\nu = \gamma_p/\pi$ [13,14], where linear anisotropy γ_p has been engineered to exceed 200 GHz [12].

Experimental efforts have focused on enhancing birefringence to control polarization dynamics in VCSELs, paving the way for ultrafast data transmission. Birefringence engineering for polarization modulation has evolved significantly over time. Early work in 1996 [15] demonstrated native birefringence splitting up to $\delta\nu \approx 30$ GHz in commercial 850 nm VCSELs. By locally modifying strain using a Ti:Sapphire laser, $\delta\nu$ was tuned between 1.5 GHz and 60 GHz, though hysteresis and long relaxation times were observed. While originally intended for polarization control and stabilization with high gain anisotropy (essentially dichroism γ_a), this laid the foundation for later developments.

In 2000 [16], in-plane anisotropic strain was introduced mechanically to reach $\delta\nu$ up to 80 GHz. The study confirmed that strain also induces gain anisotropy, which can increase dichroism γ_a and suppress polarization switching at high birefringence values.

A breakthrough came in 2015 [17], achieving $\delta\nu = 259$ GHz by applying direct mechanical stress on the VCSEL chip. While demonstrating ultrafast polarization dynamics, this method introduced high mechanical stress, limiting device longevity and compactness.

To address this, alternative methods such as piezoelectric substrates ($\delta\nu = 67$ GHz) and asymmetric heating ($\delta\nu = 79$ GHz) were explored. However, both faced practical limitations, including insufficient strain and increased power consumption.

Surface gratings then emerged as a compact and fabrication-compatible alternative. In 2019 [14], integrated gratings achieved birefringence splitting of 82–98 GHz. Unlike traditional gratings, designed mainly for polarization stability, these were optimized to minimize dichroism γ_a . However, increased etch depth led to mode confinement losses, negatively affecting photon lifetimes τ .

This approach was refined in 2023 [18] through dynamic measurements of spin-VCSELs, incorporating γ_a . Birefringence-induced mode splitting ranged from 23 GHz to 77 GHz, depending on the grating parameters. The study confirmed that surface gratings stabilize polarization without preventing polarization oscillations. Higher birefringence also increased damping, likely due to greater effective dichroism γ_a or shorter lifetimes τ . For a grating with $L = 0.41 \mu\text{m}$, $f = 0.5$, and $d = 0.16$ nm, polarization oscillations reached 68 GHz, an order of magnitude higher than VCSEL intensity dynamics. These studies demonstrate that polarization-based modulation can outperform conventional intensity modulation and emphasize the need for near-zero dichroism combined with high birefringence.

Thus, achieving high birefringence alone is insufficient; it must be balanced with minimal dichroism. This work focuses on optimizing γ_p , γ_a , and τ to ensure efficient ultrafast dynamics. Beyond designed anisotropies, interface anisotropy and non-linear dichroism—though relatively weak—contributes to native gain anisotropy [19], which damps polarization oscillations. With our approach, we can easily compensate this effect adjusting design parameters so that intrinsic linear and non-linear dichroism is effectively canceled.

Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that the polarization modulation bandwidth is nearly independent on its pumping conditions. So even just above threshold with low pump power, extremely high modulation bandwidths can be achieved, suppressing the nonlinear effects typically associated with high-energy pump operation and leading to low energy per bit operation [20].

2. 1D GaAs grating design

VCSELs inherently lack a preferred polarization due to the cylindrical symmetry of the resonator and the polarization-independent nature of Bragg mirrors. Some polarization preference may arise from the electro-optic effect induced by electric fields, aligning with the crystal axes [12,21]. However, since the cavity maintains identical optical properties for both polarization modes, they remain degenerate. As a result, small variations in operating conditions, such as

Fig. 1. Illustration of the simulated VCSEL with a grating. The DBRs are GaAs-AlGaAs based, with layer thicknesses designed for emission at $\lambda = 980$ nm, as detailed in Table 1.

temperature fluctuations or mechanical stress, can trigger polarization switching, an undesirable and unpredictable effect.

To ensure reliable VCSEL performance in optical communication, polarization stability must be enforced by introducing anisotropy. This requires decoupling the polarization modes with strong anisotropic effects and anchoring them to a controllable parameter, such as differing gain thresholds when their lifetimes are unequal.

Table 1. Table of parameters for VCSEL with grating before optimizing for ultrafast dynamics

Layer name	Material	d (nm)	Opt. function
1D Grating	GaAs	0-1000	[22]
Cap layer	P-GaAs	69.5	[22]
Top DBR 15x			
	P-Al _{0.757} GaAs	79.6	[23]
	P-GaAs	69.5	[22]
	P-Al _{0.757} GaAs	63.7	[23]
Layer for oxide			
	P-AlAs	15.9	[24]
	P-GaAs	69.5	[22]
	P-Al _{0.757} GaAs	79.6	[23]
QW			
	GaAs	136.3	[22]
	In _{0.22} GaAs	8	[25]
	GaAs	136.3	[22]
Bottom DBR 29x			
	N-Al _{0.757} GaAs	79.6	[23]
	N-GaAs	69.5	[22]
	N-Al _{0.757} GaAs	79.6	[23]
Substrate	N-GaAs		[22]

A highly effective source of anisotropy is a surface grating, an approach we investigate in this work. We place a monolithic grating [26] on top of a VCSEL structure designed for emission at

$\lambda = 980$ nm, as illustrated in Fig. 1, with specific layer parameters listed in Table 1. The grating consists of an infinite series of parallel GaAs lamellae extending indefinitely along the y -axis. As shown in Table 1, the periodic structure is defined by its pitch along the x -axis (L), the fill factor (f)—representing the fraction of the period occupied by material, with the remainder being air—and the lamella thickness along the z -axis (d_{grat}).

Introducing a structure with different effective permittivities in the x - and y -directions modifies the VCSEL's resonance condition λ , leading to distinct resonant wavelengths along these axes, i.e., $\lambda_x \neq \lambda_y$. As discussed in Sec. 3, this effect is amplified when the grating is positioned closer to the active region, as it interacts more strongly with the electromagnetic energy confined within the cavity. The corresponding field patterns—and consequently their emission polarizations—are orthogonal. These two modes are referred to as 'TE' and 'TM,' polarized along the y - and x -axes, respectively.

The selection of L , f , and d follows a specific rationale. In high-refractive-index gratings, three scattering regimes exist depending on the wavelength: diffraction, high reflectivity, and effective permittivity, as illustrated in Fig. 2. Due to the scalability of Maxwell's equations, adjusting the grating pitch L shifts these regions to different wavelengths. This enables a grating design that satisfies two key objectives: first, ensuring that the emission falls within the high-reflectivity regime, and second, maintaining manufacturing feasibility. Although UV lithography can achieve resolutions as small as 10 nm, our goal is to design a grating that can be fabricated using cost-effective large-scale production methods. These constraints define the following limits on the grating pitch L :

1. The lower limit is determined by the resolution of commonly used direct laser lithography systems, requiring $L \cdot f$ to be at least a few hundred nanometers.
2. The upper limit is set by the VCSEL's emission wavelength, $\lambda = 980$ nm.

Fig. 2. Calculated TM reflectivity on GaAs grating. The band edge shifts as period increases from $L = 0.28 \mu\text{m}$ to $0.56 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.84 \mu\text{m}$, scaling by factors of 2 and 3, respectively. This vertical shift of boundaries is independent on f and is identical for TE polarization.

As shown in Fig. 2(c), the high-reflectivity regime for $\lambda = 980$ nm can be achieved by selecting $L = 0.84 \mu\text{m}$, which represents the upper limit of the feasible range. The lamella thickness d is then chosen within $0-1 \mu\text{m}$, as the high-reflectivity region is broad enough to accommodate a range of d values. The fill factor f is subsequently optimized to ensure high reflectivity for both TE and TM modes at $\lambda = 980$ nm, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The optimization process is performed using Fourier modal method [27] and is outlined below.

First, we start with a very small L , positioning the upper edge of the high-reflectivity region near λ , then gradually increase it in steps until it approaches the lower edge of the same region. Ultimately, $L = 0.84 \mu\text{m}$ is selected, as its lower reflectivity edge aligns with the onset of the DBR's near-100% reflectivity regime.

Fig. 3. R_{TE} and R_{TM} were filtered above 70% and their difference was computed to identify regions enhancing photon lifetime. Red/blue areas highlight increased loss anisotropy, guiding the optimization of f for minimized polarization-dependent losses.

Varying the fill factor f primarily affects the slope and frequency of patterns in the second regime of the grating. The key objective is to optimize f to achieve high reflectivity at λ for both TE and TM modes while maintaining comparable reflectivity values for the two polarizations. A significant mismatch in photon lifetimes would increase dichroism, which is undesirable. To address this, we calculate the reflectivity of both polarizations for a GaAs grating with $L = 0.84 \mu\text{m}$ across a range of d_{grat} values, adjusting f to identify a region where $R_{TE}, R_{TM} \geq 70\%$ at 980 nm. This optimization approach is presented in Fig. 3, leading to the selection of $f = 0.6$, as it satisfies the reflectivity conditions over the widest range of grating thicknesses.

3. Optimizing dynamic parameters

The frequency difference between the TE and TM modes determines the rate at which the cavity can switch between them, making it desirable to maximize this separation. This effect, known as phase anisotropy [19], is denoted by γ_p and defined as:

$$\gamma_p = \pi c \frac{|\Re(\lambda_{TE} - \lambda_{TM})|}{[\Re(\lambda_{TE} + \lambda_{TM})/2]^2} \approx \pi c \left| \frac{1}{\Re(\lambda_{TE})} - \frac{1}{\Re(\lambda_{TM})} \right| \quad (1)$$

where λ_{TE} and λ_{TM} are the resonant wavelengths of the TE and TM modes, respectively. The approximation holds when the resonant wavelengths are of the same order of magnitude. This phase anisotropy translates into a frequency splitting given by $\delta\nu = \gamma_p/\pi$ [13,14]. Experimentally, the polarization oscillation (PO) frequency $\hat{\nu}$ closely follows $\delta\nu$ as long as the coupled spin-polarization dynamics is sufficiently fast and the spin-flip rate γ_s is high enough [12].

In contrast, differences in the imaginary part of the mode frequencies lead to loss anisotropy [28], denoted as γ_a :

$$\gamma_a = \frac{|\Im(\omega_{TE}) - \Im(\omega_{TM})|}{2} \quad (2)$$

where the mode frequency is given by $\omega_{TE,TM} = 2\pi c/\lambda_{TE,TM}$. Loss anisotropy contributes to polarization damping and must be minimized, as it reduces the frequency splitting according to $\delta\nu = (\gamma_p - \alpha\gamma_a)/\pi$ [12], where α is the linewidth enhancement factor, typically ranging from 1 to 5 [13]. The negative contribution to frequency splitting is negligible if the dichroism γ_a is orders of magnitude smaller than the phase anisotropy γ_p .

These effects define the objective of the optimization process: maximizing γ_p while minimizing γ_a . Since the grating period and fill factor were established in Sec. 2, the remaining degree of freedom is the grating thickness. We have used Plane-Wave Admittance Method [29] to analyze fundamental VCSEL modes with both TE and TM polarizations for d_{grat} ranging from 0 to 1 μm . At $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.58 \mu\text{m}$, we identified a pair of modes with high photon lifetimes and a phase

anisotropy of $\gamma_p = 159$ GHz, corresponding to a frequency splitting of $\delta\nu = \gamma_p/\pi = 51$ GHz, along with a loss anisotropy of $\gamma_a = 14.8$ ns⁻¹, as determined by [Eq. (1)] and [Eq. (2)].

The high photon lifetimes (exceeding 5 ps, as shown in Fig. 4(a) and 4(b)) ensure viable operation at realistic gain levels in the active region. Additional viable modes were found at $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.30$ μm , exhibiting lower lifetimes (3.4 ps for TE, 3.3 ps for TM), a smaller frequency splitting of 119 GHz, but significantly reduced dichroism at 3.8 ns⁻¹.

Fig. 4. (a, b) Calculated resonant wavelengths with photon lifetimes denoted by color for TE and TM modes. (c) phase anisotropy γ_p and dichroism γ_a (color) for VCSEL with top-DBR of 15 pairs and GaAs grating with $L = 0.84$ μm , $f = 0.6$, and gray dashed vertical line highlighting $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.58$ μm

These results demonstrate that incorporating a grating positively impacts polarization switching speed, which, in our case, corresponds to the frequency separation of 30–50 GHz. However, this value remains comparable to the switching speed of intensity-modulated sources. To make polarization modulation a competitive approach for data transmission, further improvements are necessary. The next step is to explore structural modifications that could further enhance phase anisotropy γ_p while reducing γ_a .

To enhance anisotropy across the entire parameter spectrum, the grating must be positioned closer to the regions of highest mode energy concentration. However, to maintain fabrication simplicity, the lamellae remain the topmost layer. This is achieved by reducing the number of top DBR pairs in the VCSEL from 15 to 10, thereby increasing birefringence (Fig. 5(c)). Because the field decays exponentially across the multilayers, reducing the amount of layers moves the grating closer to the cavity where the average light intensity is higher, so the impact of the grating is higher. The effect of DBR's pair removal on the grating's efficiency is illustrated in Fig. 6(a) and 6(b). While this reduction decreases photon lifetimes τ_{ph} , the 1D grating was designed for high reflectivity to compensate.

Fig. 5. Subfigures represent the same data as in Fig. 4, but for VCSEL with top-DBR of 10 pairs and GaAs grating: $L = 0.84 \mu\text{m}$, $f = 0.6$, gray dashed vertical line highlighting $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.58 \mu\text{m}$.

Simulations of this modified structure confirmed a significant increase in phase anisotropy to $\gamma_p = 594 \text{ GHz}$ at the previously optimized parameters $L = 0.84 \mu\text{m}$, $f = 0.6$, and $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.58 \mu\text{m}$. Photon lifetimes remain viable at $\geq 2 \text{ ps}$. However, the relative loss between TE and TM modes increased to $\gamma_a = 32.5 \text{ ns}^{-1}$, an unacceptable level that would induce rapid polarization damping, as discussed in Sec. 1.

To achieve ultrafast data transfer, minimizing γ_a is crucial. A highly effective method is increasing the cap layer thickness d_{cap} [30,31], as shown in Figs. 7(b). Increasing d_{cap} modifies the optical path and phase conditions at the top interface, effectively tuning the cavity resonance differently for each polarization due to the grating-induced birefringence. This enables selective compensation of modal losses and can reduce polarization-dependent loss by enhancing constructive interference for one mode over the other. For a grating with its thickness reduced to $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.23 \mu\text{m}$, we can achieve the same lifetimes while retaining significant separation of the resonant wavelengths (Fig. 7(a)). This is because the grating layer induces anisotropic effective permittivities, leading to different phase shifts and naturally reducing loss along one direction, similar to the effect of modifying d_{grat} directly.

Increasing d_{cap} eliminates the previously observed modes at $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.58 \mu\text{m}$ while compensating for losses in mode pairs at $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.23 \mu\text{m}$ when $d_{\text{cap}} = 105 \text{ nm}$. As shown in Fig. 5(c), these modes originally appeared at $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.30 \mu\text{m}$ but shifted due to the cap layer modification. This adjustment increases phase anisotropy to $\gamma_p = 711 \text{ GHz}$ while reducing loss anisotropy to $\gamma_a = 8.7 \text{ ns}^{-1}$. However, the photon lifetime τ_{ph} remains below 1 ps, causing extremely high threshold or even preventing lasing at all. Hence, this issue must be addressed.

(a) Field profiles, 15 top-DBR pairs, $L = 0.84 \mu\text{m}$, $f = 0.6$, $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.58 \mu\text{m}$

(b) Field profiles, 10 top-DBR pairs, $L = 0.84 \mu\text{m}$, $f = 0.6$, $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.58 \mu\text{m}$

Fig. 6. An example of field distribution profile. a) In the original structure shown in Table 1, the top-DBR has 15 pairs and only a small portion of the field interacts with the grating. b) After removing 5 pairs, the grating is placed closer to the active region and interacts with a larger portion of the intensity.

To compensate for the reduced $\tau_{\text{TE, TM}}$, one approach is to increase the minimum acceptable grating reflectivity R , though this significantly narrows the range of suitable parameters. Nevertheless, we compare R for TE and TM polarization modes, filtering out values below 85% (Fig. 8). The fill factor f is adjusted to shift high- R regions into alignment with the DBR high-reflectivity band. Ideally, R_{TE} and R_{TM} should be similar to avoid introducing additional dichroism γ_a .

For the investigated structure, f was optimized to 0.4 in iterative steps (Fig. 8). As expected, $\tau_{\text{TE, TM}}$ increased to 2.70 ps (TE) and 2.81 ps (TM) under these conditions. However, since f is the second optimized parameter, altering it at this stage unpredictably affects previous fine-tuning for γ_p and γ_a . This raises a critical question: can TE and TM losses be reduced without interfering with subsequent design steps?

The dependence of resonant wavelengths and photon lifetimes on the fill factor f is highly nonlinear and varies with different grating thicknesses. Figure 9 illustrates this relation for $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.25 \mu\text{m}$. For this thickness, decreasing f from 0.6 to 0.4 increases τ_{TE} from 0.94 ps to 2.70 ps and τ_{TM} from 0.80 ps to 2.81 ps. Additionally, λ_{TE} shifts down by 0.70 nm, while λ_{TM} decreases by 0.39 nm, leading to enhanced phase splitting.

With the modified fill factor, the effective index of the grating changes, necessitating a recalculation of the optimal cap thickness d_{cap} to equalize losses between both polarizations. As shown in Fig. 10, the new optimal d_{cap} is 100 nm, where the lifetime curves of both modes intersect while maintaining distinct resonant wavelengths. This underscores cap thickness as a crucial parameter for minimizing loss anisotropy γ_a and achieving balanced photon lifetimes between polarization modes. Moreover, it can be further adjusted to eliminate both linear gain

(b) $L = 0.84 \mu\text{m}$, $f = 0.6$, $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.23 \mu\text{m}$

Fig. 7. Cap thickness d_{cap} tuning to equalize lifetimes for mode groups at $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.58 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.23 \mu\text{m}$. The gray dashed vertical line marks $d_{\text{cap}} = 105 \text{ nm}$, which minimizes loss differences while preserving birefringence.

Fig. 8. Reflectivities R_{TE} and R_{TM} were filtered above 85%, narrowing the range of suitable parameters. The fill factor f was adjusted from 0.6 to 0.4 to shift a low-dichroism region to the target wavelength for the current VCSEL design.

anisotropy (resulting from the intrinsic interface anisotropy) and non-linear effective dichroism, which are otherwise challenging to mitigate, as discussed in Sec. 1.

Fig. 9. Modes with high photon lifetime (color) identified by tuning the fill factor f . These modes shifted from $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.25 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ to $0.23 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ due to cap thickness adjustment. The gray dashed vertical line marks the original $f = 0.6$, while the gray dash-dotted line indicates the new $f = 0.4$ with reflectivity above 85%.

Fig. 10. Cap thickness dependence of λ and τ for the structure where lifetimes have been regained. The gray dashed vertical line highlights cap thickness $d_{\text{cap}} = 100 \text{ nm}$, which equalizes the lifetimes for both modes. This tuning safely reduces dichroism γ_a while ensuring only continuous variations in $\lambda_{\text{TE,TM}}$ and $\tau_{\text{TE,TM}}$.

Table 2 summarizes all modifications to the original VCSEL, yielding the results shown in Fig. 11. For the optimized design, $\tau_{\text{TE}} = 2.681 \text{ ps}$ and $\tau_{\text{TM}} = 2.682 \text{ ps}$. The final reduction of d_{cap} minimizes dichroism to $\gamma_a = 0.01 \text{ ns}^{-1}$ while achieving a high phase anisotropy of $\gamma_p = 889 \text{ GHz}$, corresponding to a frequency splitting of $\delta\nu = 283 \text{ GHz}$.

Table 2. Table of parameters for VCSEL with grating optimized for ultrafast polarization switching

Layer name	Material	d (nm)	L (nm)	f (-)
1D Grating	GaAs	25	840	40%
Cap layer	P-GaAs	100		
Top DBR 10x	...			

Fig. 11. These subfigures represent the same data as in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, but for a VCSEL with a top-DBR of 10 pairs, a 100 nm thick cap layer, and a GaAs grating. The parameters are $L = 0.84 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ and $f = 0.4$, with the gray dashed line highlighting $d_{\text{grat}} = 0.25 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$. Compared to previous field profiles, the optical field is the most intense within the grating for both TE and TM modes.

4. Manufacturing inaccuracies

This section evaluates whether the numerically optimized structure tolerates realistic fabrication errors. The proposed manufacturing process proceeds as follows. First, the standard VCSEL structure is grown using molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) and etched into a mesa shape. Grating patterning can be achieved via optical (maskless) lithography, which provides precise control over the lamella width $W = L(1 - f)$, suitable for our case with feature sizes of a few hundred nanometers. The lamellae can then be fabricated either by GaAs PVD sputtering and lift-off or by etching into the cap layer using inductively coupled plasma reactive ion etching (ICP-RIE). In this work, we assume the latter method, as it offers high selectivity and anisotropy, making it ideal for defining rectangular grating profiles.

The most critical parameter is the grating thickness d_{grat} , as it is determined by etching time. It is therefore essential to quantify the allowable fabrication tolerance that preserves ultrafast modulation properties. Figure 12 shows how a deviation of $\pm 20 \text{ nm}$ affects key modal properties. As seen in Fig. 12(a), the phase anisotropy γ_p varies by about $\pm 100 \text{ GHz}$. Importantly, Fig. 12(b) reveals that the desired low dichroism is maintained only within a few nanometers around $d_{\text{grat}} = 250 \text{ nm}$. This behavior arises because the TE-mode photon lifetime (Fig. 12(c)) remains nearly constant, while the TM-mode lifetime (Fig. 12(d)) is more sensitive to geometrical variations.

Fig. 12. Calculated modal properties for the VCSEL with a surface grating defined by $L = 0.84 \mu\text{m}$ and $f = 0.4$, shown across small variations of d_{cap} and d_{grat} .

It is important to note that in the proposed process, d_{grat} and d_{cap} are not independent: over-etching simultaneously increases d_{grat} and reduces d_{cap} , as both result from etching the same layer via ICP-RIE.

From Fig. 12, we observe that etching inaccuracy most critically affects γ_a . In contrast, γ_p remains relatively stable along a diagonal trajectory in the $d_{\text{grat}}-d_{\text{cap}}$ parameter space. Targeting $d_{\text{grat}} = 250 \text{ nm}$ and $d_{\text{cap}} = 100 \text{ nm}$, we find that $\gamma_a < 20 \text{ ns}^{-1}$ [12] is maintained for d_{grat} between 247 nm and 254 nm. However, imperfections in optical lithography may result in fill factor deviations of a few percent. Since f primarily affects the lifetime of only one mode, the allowed tolerance range shifts accordingly. As shown in Fig. 13, for a nominal $f = 41\%$ and $\pm 1\%$ lithographic deviation, any d_{grat} between 248 nm and 254 nm (corresponding to $d_{\text{cap}} = 96\text{--}102 \text{ nm}$) ensures sufficiently low dichroism for ultrafast polarization modulation.

Additionally, etching may not produce perfectly rectangular lamellae. To account for realistic fabrication outcomes, we simulated $\pm 5 \text{ nm}$ deviations from vertical sidewalls, as shown in Fig. 14.

In the case of an undercut, the anisotropy is enhanced: γ_p increases to 987 GHz, and the photon lifetimes slightly decrease to $\tau_{\text{TE}} = 2.349 \text{ ps}$ and $\tau_{\text{TM}} = 2.590 \text{ ps}$. This yields a frequency splitting $\delta\nu = 314 \text{ GHz}$ and dichroism $\gamma_a = 9.89 \text{ ns}^{-1}$. Conversely, an extra 5 nm of unetched material weakens phase anisotropy to $\gamma_p = 813 \text{ GHz}$, while increasing the lifetimes to $\tau_{\text{TE}} = 2.783 \text{ ps}$ and $\tau_{\text{TM}} = 2.761 \text{ ps}$. This corresponds to $\delta\nu = 259 \text{ GHz}$ and $\gamma_a = 0.72 \text{ ns}^{-1}$. Both configurations meet the requirements for reliable polarization modulation at 250 Gbps bandwidth.

Fig. 13. Tolerance of the optimized parameters for low dichroism γ_a . The dashed gray line marks the threshold $\gamma_a = 20 \text{ ns}^{-1}$. The solid red line indicates the range of acceptable etching errors considering different fill factors f .

Fig. 14. Phase anisotropy γ_p and dichroism γ_a (color) for the final optimized VCSEL from Fig. 11 and Table 2, influenced by 5 nm undercut and sidewall tapering.

5. Conclusion

We have simulated VCSELs with surface gratings using Fourier modal method, directly addressing the need for "VCSELs with integrated and fabrication ready birefringence control which can be used for ultra-fast polarization dynamics" [18]. Our results demonstrate that precise tailoring of grating parameters enables phase anisotropy γ_p while simultaneously minimizing loss anisotropy γ_a , which traditionally increases with birefringence. We have shown multiple parameter configurations and their shortages, and have arrived at a configuration which supports ultrafast dynamics. Importantly, this optimization is achieved while maintaining practical photon lifetimes τ . Previous approaches to achieving strong birefringence have relied on non-compact structures with limited attention to dichroism.

This optimization is achieved by carefully tuning the grating parameters. The period width L is adjusted to move the grating's high-reflectivity regime to the emission wavelength. Both f and d_{grat} greatly impact γ_p and γ_a — f serves the purpose of matching the high reflectivity region of the TM mode to the TE mode while d_{grat} maximizes the birefringence. These parameters are chosen together; $f = 0.4$ creates a high reflectivity overlap on a large interval of d_{grat} . The chosen thickness $0.25 \mu\text{m}$ causes constructive interference for both orthogonal modes while making their resonant wavelength differ. Cap thickness, $d_{\text{cap}} = 0.100 \mu\text{m}$ in this case, phase shifts the two modes differently to equalize their lifetimes. Furthermore, this method provides a potential approach for compensating for interface anisotropy, a typically uncontrolled source of dichroism in VCSELs.

The final chosen configuration ensures that the grating introduces the maximum possible birefringence without becoming a new source of dichroism, which would be detrimental to ultrafast polarization modulation. Future developments will be dedicated to the dynamical and non-linear effects of the designed structure and their impact on ultra-fast modulation and switching by combining the generalized spin-flip model and RCWA approach used here.

Funding. Grantová Agentura České Republiky (25-15775S); Ministerstvo Školství, Mládeže a Tělovýchovy (SP2025/090, Student Grant Competition, VSB-TUO); Ministerstvo Školství, Mládeže a Tělovýchovy (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631, MATUR); Ministerstvo Životního Prostředí (CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048, REFRESH).

Disclosures. The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

References

1. P. Moser, "Energy-efficient vcsels for optical interconnects," Ph.D. thesis, Technical University of Berlin (2016).
2. A. Larsson, E. Simpanen, J. Gustavsson, *et al.*, "1060 nm vcsels for long-reach optical interconnects," *Opt. Fiber Technol.* **44**, 36–42 (2018).
3. L. Chorcho, L. Szostkiewicz, N. Ledentsov, *et al.*, "6 core fiber and vcsel based interferometer sensor for motion or vibration monitoring," *Opt. Laser Technol.* **162**, 109249 (2023).
4. A. Liu, P. Wolf, J. Lott, *et al.*, "Vertical-cavity surface-emitting lasers for data communication and sensing," *Photonics Res.* **7**(2), 121 (2019).
5. G. Roelkens, L. Liu, D. Liang, *et al.*, "Iii-v/silicon photonics for on-chip and intra-chip optical interconnects," *Laser Photonics Rev.* **4**(6), 751–779 (2010).
6. J. Goyvaerts, A. Grabowski, J. Gustavsson, *et al.*, "Enabling vcsel-on-silicon nitride photonic integrated circuits with micro-transfer-printing," *Optica* **8**(12), 1573 (2021).
7. N. Haghighi, G. Larisch, R. Rosales, *et al.*, "35 ghz bandwidth with directly current modulated 980 nm oxide aperture single cavity vcsels," in *2018 IEEE International Semiconductor Laser Conference (ISLC)*, (2018), pp. 1–2.
8. N. Ledentsov, M. Agustin, V. Shchukin, *et al.*, "Quantum dot 850 nm vcsels with extreme high temperature stability operating at bit rates up to 25 Gbit/s at 150°C," *Solid-State Electron.* **155**, 150–158 (2019).
9. H. Altug, D. Englund, and J. Vuckovic, "Photonic crystal surface mode laser," (2007), pp. 1–2.
10. S. Hallstein, J. D. Berger, M. Hilpert, *et al.*, "Manifestation of coherent spin precession in stimulated semiconductor emission dynamics," *Phys. Rev. B* **56**(12), R7076–R7079 (1997).
11. P. Pérez, A. Valle, and L. Pesquera, "Polarization-resolved characterization of long-wavelength vertical-cavity surface-emitting laser parameters," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* **31**(11), 2574–2580 (2014).
12. M. Lindemann, G. Xu, T. Pusch, *et al.*, "Ultrafast spin-lasers," *Nature* **568**(7751), 212–215 (2019).
13. M. Drong, T. Fördös, H. Jaffrès, *et al.*, "Spin-vcsels with local optical anisotropies: Toward terahertz polarization modulation," *Phys. Rev. Appl.* **15**(1), 014041 (2021).
14. T. Pusch, P. Debernardi, M. Lindemann, *et al.*, "Vertical-cavity surface-emitting laser with integrated surface grating for high birefringence splitting," *Electron. Lett.* **55**(19), 1055–1057 (2019).
15. A. K. Jansen van Doorn, M. P. van Exter, and J. P. Woerdman, "Tailoring the birefringence in a vertical-cavity semiconductor laser," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **69**(24), 3635–3637 (1996).
16. K. Panajotov, B. Nagler, G. Verschaffelt, *et al.*, "Impact of in-plane anisotropic strain on the polarization behavior of vertical-cavity surface-emitting lasers," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **77**(11), 1590–1592 (2000).
17. M. Hofmann, T. Pusch, M. Lindemann, *et al.*, "Vertical-cavity surface-emitting lasers with birefringence splitting above 250 GHz," *Electron. Lett.* **51**, 83–85 (2015).
18. M. Lindemann, N. Jung, N. Manrique-Nieto, *et al.*, "Polarization dynamics in spin-vcsels with integrated surface grating for high birefringence splitting," *Electron. Lett.* **59**(13), e12827 (2023).
19. T. Fördös, H. Jaffrès, K. Postava, *et al.*, "Eigenmodes of spin vertical-cavity surface-emitting lasers with local linear birefringence and gain dichroism," *Phys. Rev. A* **96**(4), 043828 (2017).
20. M. Lindemann, G. Xu, T. Pusch, *et al.*, "Ultrafast spin-lasers for optical data communication," in *2019 Conference on Lasers and Electro-Optics Europe and European Quantum Electronics Conference*, (Optica Publishing Group, 2019).
21. M. P. van Exter, A. K. Jansen van Doorn, and J. P. Woerdman, "Electro-optic effect and birefringence in semiconductor vertical-cavity lasers," *Phys. Rev. A* **56**(1), 845–853 (1997).
22. T. Skauli, P. Kuo, K. Vodopyanov, *et al.*, "Improved dispersion relations for gaas and applications to nonlinear optics," *J. Appl. Phys.* **94**(10), 6447–6455 (2003).
23. S. Gehrsitz, F. Reinhard, C. Gourgon, *et al.*, "The refractive index of Al_xGa_{1-x}As below the band gap: Accurate determination and empirical modeling," *J. Appl. Phys.* **87**(11), 7825–7837 (2000).
24. A. Rakic and M. Majewski, "Modeling the optical dielectric function of gaas and alas: Extension of adachi's model," *J. Appl. Phys.* **80**(10), 5909–5914 (1996).
25. S. Adachi, "Optical dispersion relations for GaP, GaAs, GaSb, InP, InAs, InSb, Al_xGa_{1-x}As, and In_{1-x}Ga_xAsyP_{1-y}," *J. Appl. Phys.* **66**(12), 6030–6040 (1989).

26. M. Gębski, M. Dems, A. Szerling, *et al.*, “Monolithic high-index contrast grating: A material independent high-reflectance VCSEL mirror,” *Opt. Express* **23**(9), 11674 (2015).
27. M. Dems, “Modelling of high-contrast grating mirrors. The impact of imperfections on their performance in VCSELs,” *Opto-Electronics Rev.* **19**(3), 340–345 (2011).
28. O. Hejtman, T. Fördös, M. Drong, *et al.*, “Spin-lasers with periodic gratings: toward ultrafast polarization modulation,” in *23rd Slovak-Czech-Polish Optical Conference on Wave and Quantum Aspects of Contemporary Optics*, (2022), p. 34.
29. M. Dems, R. Kotynski, and K. Panajotov, “Plane Wave Admittance Method — a novel approach for determining the electromagnetic modes in photonic structures,” *Opt. Express* **13**(9), 3196 (2005).
30. P. P. Baveja, B. Kögel, P. Westbergh, *et al.*, “Impact of photon lifetime on thermal rollover in 850-nm high-speed VCSELs,” in *Vertical-Cavity Surface-Emitting Lasers XVI*, vol. 8276 C. Lei and K. D. Choquette, eds., International Society for Optics and Photonics (SPIE, 2012), p. 82760V.
31. P. Westbergh, J. Gustavsson, B. Kögel, *et al.*, “Speed enhancement of vcsels by photon lifetime reduction,” *Electron. Lett.* **46**(13), 938–940 (2010).